

Iris Pallida Ecological Needs and Agrotechniques

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Propagation of *Iris pallida* for subsequent cultivation in agroforestry system with almond trees

Iris pallida is a widespread crop in France and Morocco, mainly grown in the Figline Valdarno and the Chianti Fiorentino in Italy. This rhizomatous Iridaceae is a species of medicinal interest typically widespread in agroforestry systems as a perennial herbaceous plant, associated for example with olive and almond groves. From the rhizomes collected in the second or third year from planting, a flour is obtained that is highly sought after by the cosmetics and perfumery industries. The distillation of the essential oils contained in the rhizome produces iris butter, a product with high added value. The soils with a balanced texture, well drained and good fertility, ensure excellent success of the Iris crop in a Mediterranean environment. The cultivation cycle of the iris typically begins in mid-September by planting vegetative sprouts derived from the rhizomes cleaning harvested in the third year of cultivation. Moderate fertilization () and irrigation help to achieve significant production which, over a three-year cycle, can reach 3.5 Mg ha⁻¹ of dry rhizome. Weeding is crucial in the first and second year of cultivation. In the third year, the *iris* will have covered the soil to the point of excluding spontaneous species. Iris, ultimately, represents a secondary associated crop in the Tuscan agronomic tradition, where it is perceived as a valid integration of the farm income produced within orchards as agrisilvicultural practices. However, the high demand for labor both in cultivation and in post-harvest operations have not allowed a wider diffusion so far. Several projects for the cultivation mechanization of cultivation as well as further steps tackling the supply chain improvement towards the marketing of flour (*face powder*) and iris distillates (*iris butter*) could favour a wider adoption of the species within the farm cultivation plans.

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